

Detection of Genes Patterns with an Enhanced Partitioning-Based DBSCAN Algorithm

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Abstract: Microarray datasets are enriched with numerous unknown gene expression patterns that may have significant biological meaning. Detecting well-separated gene expression patterns is a critical task in microarray data analysis. The density-based spatial clustering DBSCAN algorithm has been used to detect patterns with different shapes and sizes in many applications. However, the DBSCAN algorithm is time-consuming when used on big datasets, and microarray datasets are considered as big and complex datasets. Therefore, in this study, we modified the DBSCAN algorithm by combining it with a partitioning around medoids algorithm based on normalized and weighted Mahalanobis distance (NWM). The developed algorithm (NWM_PDBSCAN) was tested on selected microarray expression datasets, which were pre-processed prior to analysis. The results revealed an optimal cluster solution with different shapes and sizes. We further reduced the dataset sizes using a random sampling technique to enhance the performance of the DBSCAN algorithm. The proposed NWM_PDBSCAN algorithm performed ideally, and was evaluated using Dunn's validity index.

Keywords: Microarray data; Partitioning around medoids; DBSCAN; Normalized weighted Mahalanobis distance; Validity index; Pre-processing; Sampling; Number of clusters

I. INTRODUCTION

Microarrays are designed to detect genes and measure their activities. Research using microarrays has contributed significantly to human health and disease, cell biology, and related areas [1]. Various kinds of technical noise exist in gene expression profile data. Pre-processing methods have been used to remove systematic noise from microarray datasets. Normalization is a computational pre-processing method that has been widely applied to microarray datasets [2], and it can improve the detection of differentially expressed genes between two or more experimental conditions [3]. In statistical terms, a gene is considered to be differentially expressed if its expression level changes between two conditions regardless of how small the change is, or it is considered to be differentially expressed only if the change is defined as significant [4]. Many approaches have been used to detect differentially expressed genes. In this study, we used fold change, calculated as the ratio of the average control values to the test sample values, combined with p-value (from t-test) to detect differentially expressed genes [5][6]. Microarray

technology produces high-dimensional data. To reduce the complexity of the microarray data, we used a feature extraction technique that converts original feature space into compact space. Principle component analysis is a popular feature extraction technique that reduces the dimensionality by transforming the original attribute space into smaller space [7]. Classical principle component analysis is not useful when the number of variables is larger than the number of observations, which is a common condition in microarray datasets. Therefore, we used principle component analysis based on the singular value decomposition of a real data matrix [8]. Observing relevant patterns and dependencies in gene expression are significant approaches in microarray data analysis. Unsupervised learning is a machine learning method in which structures are found without using labels [9]. In microarray data analysis, an initial approach has been the clustering of a group of genes with similar changes in expression. Clustering is an unsupervised classification method that collects data objects with high similarity into the same cluster, and separates data objects that are dissimilar. Clustering of gene expression data can be performed either by grouping

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genes with similar expression across conditions or by grouping samples with similar expression patterns across all genes [10]. We used the partitioning around medoids (PAM) algorithm based on normalized and weighted Mahalanobis distance (NWM) to partition the selected microarray datasets into k subsets. The NWM_PAM algorithm used normalized and weighted features of microarray expression datasets according to their distances to obtain an ideal cluster solution. However, the NWM_PAM algorithm detected fixed shapes patterns, whereas microarray datasets are enriched with gene expression patterns with no limit of shapes and sizes, and some of these patterns may have significant biological meaning. Therefore, we modified the DBSCAN algorithm by combining it with the NWM_PAM algorithm. The classical DBSCAN algorithm is a well-known density-based spatial clustering algorithm that is not limited to shapes of clusters and, therefore, can detect patterns with arbitrary shapes [11]. The DBSCAN algorithm requires two parameters to generate clusters: the minimum number of points, and ϵ -neighborhood value. However, DBSCAN is time-consuming when used on big datasets because it works on entire datasets, and microarray expression datasets are considered as big and complex datasets. We further reduced the sizes of the selected microarray datasets by random sampling, which is a technique that is commonly used to enhance clustering of large datasets [12]. A simple random sampling method selects data unit by unit with equal probability of selection for all units [13]. The algorithm that we developed (NWM_PDBSCAN) overcomes the drawbacks of the classical DBSCAN algorithm. NWM_PDBSCAN first partitions microarray datasets into k ideal partitions, then samples equally on the ideal partitions using simple random sampling without replacement to reduce the sizes of microarray datasets and enhance clustering. We tested NWM_PDBSCAN with different numbers of minimum points and various ϵ -neighborhood values on two microarray expression datasets, and used Dunn's validity index [14] to evaluate the detected gene expression patterns.

I. METHODOLOGY

A. Partitioning around medoids algorithm using normalized and weighted Mahalanobis distance (NWM_PAM)

The PAM algorithm was first proposed by Kaufman

and Rousseeuw [15]. It is one of the k -medoids approaches that is most widely used because it is robust in handling noise and outliers. Medoids differ from means in that they are consistently part of a dataset. A medoid static indicates the minimal average dissimilarity of a medoid from the other points in a dataset [16][17]. The PAM algorithm aims to randomly partition datasets into k subsets and then improve cluster medoids iteratively to minimize the objective function (Fig. 1). The number of k partitions is chosen so that a random set of k partitions are considered to be medoids. The non-medoids items are inspected in each step, in order to swap existing medoids with non-medoids items to improve the quality of the clusters. Quality is measured by the sum of all distances from non-medoid objects to medoids in a cluster. The PAM algorithm depends on the underlying distance. The measures of features involved in the partitioning process are continuously increasing as a result of technology advancements. The features have various degrees of relevance in real-world datasets, and relevant features may differ in degrees of relevance. The distance measure for features can have a critical influence on the classification methods, where patterns that have small distances are similar in the features space. The distances measures have their own strengths and weaknesses, therefore distance measures should be chosen that match application needs. The traditional Mahalanobis distance is one of the fundamental and widely used distances in classification. Mahalanobis distance is defined as:

$$D_i^{Mahalanobis} = \sqrt{(x-u_i)^T \Sigma_i^{-1} (x-u_i)} \quad (1)$$

where, x is the sample vector to classify, and Σ_i^{-1} is the inverse matrix of groups covariance of class $\{I\}$.

The Mahalanobis distance is considered as an appropriate function if the samples are multivariate normal distributed [18]. The Mahalanobis distance has some limitations. For example, equal adding up of normalized squared distances of features performs ideally if the data are clean, but not, for example, if a feature has a high value and covers the information provided by other features, which leads to misclassification. Another limitation of Mahalanobis distance, which we noted when it was used with the PAM algorithm on our selected microarray dataset, was

that it sometimes caused a large cluster to attract a member of neighboring clusters, and this might produce unusually large or small clusters. We used Mahalanobis distance as the basis of the normalized and weighted distance metric in our analyses of microarray datasets. The integrated NWM_PAM algorithm (Fig. 1) was used so that each cluster attracted the data points (genes) that optimized its own shape, as inherited by the covariance matrix of the samples within that cluster [19][20].

The NWM distance is defined as:

$$NWM = \sqrt{\frac{1}{w^2} (W_D (x - u_i)) \Sigma^{-1} (W_D (x - u_i))} \quad (2)$$

where, W_D is the diagonal weight matrix, Σ^{-1} is the inverse matrix of groups covariance, and W^2 is the squared weight normalized factor and is equal to (W_D^2) .

Input
 $M = \{ m_1, m_2, \dots, m_n \}$ // set of elements,
 A // adjacency matrix showing distance between elements based on normalized and weighted Mahalanobis distance, and
 k // number of desired clusters.

Output
 K // set of clusters.

PAM algorithm
 Arbitrary select k medoids from M .
 Repeat
 For each m_k not a medoid do the following:
 For each medoid m_i
 Compute square error function Q_{ih} ;
 Find I, h where the Q is the smallest;
 If $Q_{ih} <$ current Q , then
 Swap medoid m_i with m_h until $Q_{ih} \geq$ current Q .
 For each $m_i \in M$
 Assign m_i to k_j where $\text{dist}(m_i, m_j)$ is minimum over all medoids.

Fig.1. The NWM_PAM algorithm

B. Random sampling

A sample can be defined as a subset of a population that represents the entire population, and can be denoted as s of size n [21]. Random sampling can be used to reduce the number of subjects included in an analysis, without biasing the findings, and with appropriate statistics, such an analysis can produce generalizable findings at low cost. Samples can also be selected using nonrandom techniques. We used a random sampling technique to reduce the number of genes in the selected microarray datasets. In simple random sampling, selections are made purely by chance.

For instance, in a population of 5000, every individual is allocated a different number. Then, a sample size of 200 is achieved simply by pulling 200 numbers out of a hat. Simple random sampling is sometimes called independent random sampling because the probability of an object being selected is independent of the identity of other selected objects. Simple random sampling is technically a valid approach for analyzing many data types [22]. The Simple random sampling can be performed with or without replacement. In this study, we used simple random sampling without replacement defined as:

$$P(S) = \begin{cases} \binom{N}{n}^{-1} & \text{if } s = n \\ 0 & \text{otherwise,} \end{cases} \quad (3)$$

A simple random sampling scheme is one in which all possible combinations of n units may be formed from a population of N units with the same chance of selection. In simple random sampling without replacement, each selected item is removed from the collection of candidate items. A unit is selected, observed, and not replaced in the population before making the next selection, and this procedure is repeated until n distinct units are selected, ignoring all repetitions [23].

C. The DBSCAN algorithm

The DBSCAN algorithm is a well-known density-based spatial clustering algorithm in which clusters are regarded as dense sets of data items separated by few dense regions [24]. The DBSCAN algorithm indicates the density reachability of clusters. Briefly, a point P is directly density-reachable from a point Q if it is not

further away than a given distance ϵ , where P is a part of the ϵ -neighborhood, and, if P is surrounded by a number of points, then P and Q can be considered as part of the same cluster. Q is density-reachable if there are a series of P points, p_1, p_2, \dots, p_n , with $p_1 = P$ and $p_n = Q$, and each p_{i+1} is directly reachable from p_i . Density reachability is illustrated in Fig. 2 [25].

Fig. 2. Density reachability of a core point P

Density reachability is not a symmetry relation, but if P is connected to Q through a point O , then they are considered as density-connected points that are asymmetric. The DBSCAN algorithm has two input parameters, ϵ -neighborhood and the minimum number of points required to produce a cluster. If an ϵ -neighborhood contains fixed points, a cluster will be formed, and the points located outside the ϵ -neighborhood will be considered as noise [26]. Density-based clustering algorithms are efficient in handling large spatial datasets, and the DBSCAN algorithm is considered to be effective and efficient in handling large spatial datasets. Moreover, the DBSCAN algorithm can perform spatial clustering, which other density-based clustering algorithms cannot.

We used the DBSCAN algorithm to cluster microarray expression datasets for the following reasons: (i) it can capturing patterns with different shapes and sizes; (ii) there is no need to predict the number of clusters; and (iii) it is a robust algorithm that can handle outliers and merge clusters if they are similar [27]. The classical DBSCAN algorithm is described in Fig. 3.

Input

Dataset S , the radius of an ϵ -neighborhood, and density threshold for minimum number of points.

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Output

Set of clusters C ($1 \leq j \leq n$), where n is the number of clusters.

DBSCAN

For ($i=l; i \leq num; i++$) // num : the number of point in dataset S .

If (p , is a core object), find all density-reachable points of p , in the ϵ -neighborhood of p .

For ($j=l, j \leq m, j++$) // m : the number of core objects in dataset S .

Find all directly density-reachable points of the core object p .

Fig. 3. Classical DBSCAN algorithm

D. Cluster validity index

The performance of the PAM algorithm was evaluated with respect to two distances metrics, outlined in section I, using Dunn's validity index. Cluster validation techniques provide analytical evaluations of the amount and type of structures detected by partitioning, and therefore, are key tools for interpreting clustering results. Dunn's index evaluates sets of clusters that are compact and well separated. For any partition $U \leftrightarrow X = X_1 \cup \dots \cup X_k$, Dunn's index is defined as:

$$D(U) = \min_{1 \leq i \leq k} \left\{ \min_{1 \leq i \leq k, j \neq i} \left\{ \frac{\delta(X_i, X_j)}{\max_{1 \leq i \leq k} \{\Delta(X_k)\}} \right\} \right\} \quad (4)$$

where $\delta(X_i, X_j)$ is the distance between clusters X_i and X_j (inter-cluster distance), $\Delta(X_k)$ is the intra-cluster distance of cluster X_k , and k is the number of clusters in partition U . The goal of Dunn's validity index is to maximize inter-cluster distances and minimize intra-cluster distances. The optimal cluster solution is the one with the highest Dunn's value [14][28].

E. Gene expression data

The microarray datasets used in this study are gene expression profiles of human hematopoietic stem cells

and adipocytes related to aging and hypoxia-induced modulation, respectively.

Hematopoietic stem cells (HSCs)

The HSC dataset contains gene expression data related to the aging process from human HSCs of young, old, and middle-aged subjects. The dataset contains 27 samples with expression data for 54614 genes [29].

Hypoxia-induced modulation

The hypoxia dataset contains gene expression data related to hypoxia-induced modulation in human adipocytes [30]. The microarrays contained 41,152 probes, and eight samples of adipocytes exposed to hypoxia (1% O₂) or normoxia (21% O₂) for 24 h were analyzed.

F. The NWM_PDBSCAN algorithm

We used the NWM_PAM algorithm to partition the two microarray datasets into k ideal subsets. The microarray datasets were pre-processed before the analysis to detect differentially expressed genes. Features of the microarray datasets were also extracted using principle component analysis based on singular value decomposition and the principle components with high variability were chosen for the gene expression analysis. The NWM distance is a robust distance metric and a good choice, especially for detecting ellipsoidal clusters shapes. It produced ideal cluster quality when integrated with the PAM algorithm and tested on microarray expression datasets. In this analysis, our aim was to detect ideal gene expression patterns in microarray datasets, which are rich with genes patterns that may have arbitrary shapes but significant biological meaning. Therefore, we adopted the DBSCAN algorithm.

Spatial data clustering is a common data mining technique used for retrieving knowledge from large spatial datasets, including microarray datasets. The DBSCAN algorithm is a spatial clustering algorithm that uses two parameters, ϵ -neighborhood and minimum number points, to iteratively connect direct density-reachable points from a core point, and merge density-reachable clusters. The process terminates when no new points can be added to any cluster. The DBSCAN algorithm clusters areas with high density, and the low-density areas are not clustered. The time-consuming and large memory requirements of the DBSCAN

algorithm were overcome by combining it with the NWM_PAM algorithm (Fig. 4).

Fig. 4. Proposed NWM_PDBSCAN algorithm

Furthermore, the microarray datasets were reduced using a random sampling technique without replacement in order to improve the scalability and time efficiency of the DBSCAN algorithm. The HSC and hypoxia microarray datasets were partitioned in the early stage of the analysis to ensure an even distribution of the sampled genes expression data. Finally, the DBSCAN algorithm was applied to the two microarray datasets to identify significant ideal genes patterns.

III. RESULTS

The proposed NWM_PDBSCAN algorithm was tested on two microarray expression datasets with different minimum number of points and ϵ -neighborhood values (Tables 1 and 2). Different numbers of clusters were generated automatically and

the quality of the patterns was assessed using Dunn's validity index.

Table 1. Evaluation of the NWM_PDBSCAN algorithm using the hypoxia dataset

Results	NWM_PDBSCAN			
	MinPts ^a	Eps ^b	K subsets produced	Validity index ^c
	30	0.5	4	0.0048
	40	0.6	3	0.0051
	50	1	2	0.0067

Were:

^aMinPts = minimum number of points

^bEps = ϵ -neighborhood value

^cDunn's = validity index.

Table 2. Evaluation of the NWM_PDBSCAN algorithm using the HSC dataset

Results	NWM_PDBSCAN			
	MinPts ^a	Eps ^b	K subsets produced	Validity index ^c
	30	0.9	5	0.0076
	37	1.05	4	0.0073
	50	1.5	2	0.0093

Were:

^aMinPts = minimum number of points

^bEps = ϵ -neighborhood value

^cDunn's = validity index.

IV. DISCUSSION

Microarray technology is used to study gene expression at time and huge amounts of data are generated. Extracting knowledge and information from such datasets is a big challenge.

Unsupervised classification (clustering) algorithms have been used to analyze and understand gene expression data. In this study, the aim was to detect gene expression patterns with arbitrary shapes that may have significant biological meaning in microarray expression data using the enhanced NWM_PDBSCAN algorithm that we developed. The proposed algorithm detected expression patterns of different shapes and sizes and with sufficient quality. First, the genes expression data were partitioned into k subsets using the NWM_PAM algorithm in order to obtain ideal k partitions. The large and complex microarray datasets may contain gene expression patterns with arbitrary shapes and significant biological meaning. The DBSCAN algorithm is a common density-based algorithm that can detect patterns with arbitrary shapes. However, DBSCAN is slow on large datasets and may not capture sufficient density areas of genes if there is variation in density area in the dataset. Therefore, we utilized a random sampling technique to enhance the clustering algorithm performance because sampling from an ideal partition will distribute the sampling process more evenly. The proposed NWM_PDBSCAN algorithm was tested on two microarray datasets and Dunn's validity index was used to assess the quality of the detected clusters. The two parameters, minimum number of points and ϵ -neighborhood, in the DBSCAN algorithm were varied to obtain patterns with both a high-density area of genes and high Dunn's index value. As shown in Tables 1 and 2, the different minimum number of points and ϵ -neighborhood values generated different numbers of k subsets with different shapes and sizes. An optimal cluster solution was obtained using the proposed NWM_PDBSCAN algorithm, the time and complexity was reduced, and the genes patterns that were obtained from the hypoxia and HSC datasets may have significant meaning.

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REFERENCES

- [1] Yin, W., Chen, T., Zhou, S. X., & Chakraborty, A. Background correction for cDNA microarray images using the TV+L1 model. *Bioinformatics*, 21, 2410-2416. 2005.

- [2] Qiu, X., Wu, H., & Hu, R. The impact of quantile and rank normalization procedures on the testing power of gene differential expression analysis. *BMC Bioinformatics*, 14, 124. 2013.
- [3] Steinhoff C. & Vingron, M. Normalization and quantification of differential expression in gene expression microarrays. *Briefings in Bioinformatics*, 7, 166-177. 2006.
- [4] McCarthy D. J. and Smyth, G. K. Testing significance relative to a fold-change threshold is a TREAT. *Bioinformatics*, 25, 765-771, 2009.
- [5] Dembélé D. & Kastner, P. Fold change rank ordering statistics: a new method for detecting differentially expressed genes. *BMC Bioinformatics*, 15, 14. 2014.
- [6] Dalman, M. R., Deeter, A., Nimishakavi, G., & Duan, Z.-H. Fold change and p-value cutoffs significantly alter microarray interpretations. *BMC Bioinformatics*, 13, S11. 2012.
- [7] Zareapoor M. & Seeja, K. Feature extraction or feature selection for text classification: A case study on phishing email detection. *International Journal of Information Engineering and Electronic Business*, 7, 60. 2015.
- [8] Praus, P. SVD-based principal component analysis of geochemical data. *Central European Journal of Chemistry*, 3, 731-741. 2005.
- [9] Libbrecht M. W. & Noble, W. S. Machine learning applications in genetics and genomics. *Nature Reviews Genetics*, 16, 321. 2015.
- [10] Kerr, G., Ruskin, H. J., Crane, M., & Doolan, P. Techniques for clustering gene expression data. *Computers in Biology and Medicine*, 38, 283-293. 2008.
- [11] Liu, P. Zhou, D., & Wu, N. VDBSCAN: varied density based spatial clustering of applications with noise. In *Service Systems and Service Management. International Conference on* (pp. 1-4). 2007.
- [12] Tang, W., Pi, D., & He, Y. A density-based clustering algorithm with sampling for travel behavior analysis. In *International Conference on Intelligent Data Engineering and Automated Learning* (pp. 231-239). 2016.
- [13] Thompson, S. K. Simple random sampling. In *Sampling, (Third Edition)*, pp. 9-37). 2012.
- [14] Bolshakova N. & Azuaje, F. Cluster validation techniques for genome expression data. *Signal Processing*, 83, 825-833. 2003.
- [15] Kaufman L., Rousseeuw, P. Clustering by means of medoids. North-Holland. 1987.
- [16] Bhat, A. K-medoids clustering using partitioning around medoids for performing face recognition. *International Journal of Soft Computing, Mathematics and Control*, 3, 1-12. 2014.
- [17] Zhou, E., Mao, S., Li, M., & Sun, Z. PAM spatial clustering algorithm research based on CUDA. In *Geoinformatics, 24th International Conference on*, (pp. 1-7). 2016.
- [18] Chen, G., Zhang, H.-G., & Guo, J. Efficient computation of Mahalanobis distance in financial hand-written Chinese character recognition, In *Machine Learning and Cybernetics, International Conference on* (pp. 2198-2201). 2007.
- [19] Wolfel M. & Ekenel, H. K. Feature weighted Mahalanobis distance: improved robustness for Gaussian classifiers. In *Signal Processing Conference, 13th European* (pp. 1-4). 2005.
- [20] Younis, K., Karim, M., Hardie, R., Loomis, J., Rogers, S., & DeSimio, M. Cluster merging based on weighted Mahalanobis distance with application in digital mammograph. In *Aerospace and Electronics Conference, NAECON 1998, Proceedings of the IEEE 1998 National* (pp. 525-530). 1988.
- [21] Singh, S. *Advanced sampling theory with applications: How Michael "Selected" Amy* (Vol. 2). Springer Science & Business Media. 2003.
- [22] Chen, C.-H., Huang, W.-T., Tan, T.-H., Chang, C.-C., & Chang, Y.-J. Using k-nearest neighbor classification to diagnose abnormal lung sounds. *Sensors*, 15, 13132-13158. 2015.
- [23] Müller, K. Accelerating weighted random sampling without replacement. *Arbeitsberichte Verkehrs-und Raumplanung* (Vol. 1141). 2016.
- [24] Yu, Y.-Q. Huang, T.-Q., Guo, G.-D., & Li, K. Semi-supervised clustering algorithm for multi-density and complex shape dataset. In *Pattern Recognition, CCPR'08. Chinese Conference on* (pp. 1-6). 2008.
- [25] Tsai C.-F. & Sung, C.-Y. EIDBSCAN: An Extended Improving DBSCAN algorithm with sampling techniques. *International Journal of Business Intelligence and Data Mining*, 5, 94-111. 2009.
- [26] Kotyrba, M., Volná, E., & Komínková Oplatková, Z. Comparison of modern clustering algorithms for two dimensional data. In *Proceedings 28th European Conference on Modelling and Simulation, ECMS 2014*. 2014.
- [27] Sharma, A., Gupta, R., & Tiwari, A. Improved Density

Based Spatial Clustering of Applications of Noise Clustering Algorithm for Knowledge Discovery in Spatial Data, *Mathematical Problems in Engineering* (Vol 2016). 2016.

- [28] Handl, J., Knowles, J., & Kell, D. B. Computational cluster validation in post-genomic data analysis. *Bioinformatics*, 21, 3201-3212. 2005.
- [29] Pang, W. W., Price, E. A., Sahoo, D., Beerman, I., Maloney, W. J., Rossi, D. J., ... & Weissman, I. L. Human bone marrow hematopoietic stem cells are increased in frequency and myeloid-biased with age. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences*, 108, 20012-20017. 2011.
- [30] Mazzatti, D., Lim, F.-L., O'Hara, A., Wood, I. S., & Trayhurn, P. A microarray analysis of the hypoxia-induced modulation of gene expression in human adipocytes. *Archives of Physiology and Biochemistry*, 118, 112-120. 2012.